

Light-matter interactions under inverted Schwarzschild space-time conditions

Aleksandr G. Avramenko

American Physical Society
ORCID: 0000-0001-5951-0150
aavramen@vivaldi.net

September 8, 2024

Abstract

Perhaps one of the most intriguing pursuits in the physical sciences is the search for a way to unify the predictions of quantum mechanics with that of general relativity. Nowhere is this need more evident than when a massive body occupies an increasingly small volume, forming a singularity surrounded by an event horizon. The singularity warps space-time requiring the need to rely on relativistic equations, while at the same time its size requires a quantum treatment. This essay attempts to go through a thought experiment which analyzes how the electrons of a small molecule would react if such a moiety tunneled through the event horizon of a non-rotating Schwarzschild black hole. We find that beyond the Schwarzschild radius an inversion of space-time occurs. This results in the need to rethink how we see the Hilbert space vectors of a quantum wavefunction.

Keywords: Perturbation theory, Hilbert space, wavefunction, space-time.

1 Introduction

Ever since Karl Schwarzschild was able to find solutions to Einstein's field equations of general relativity describing the behavior of gravitational fields near a point-like mass scientists have pondered about the behavior of matter around such an object. Early 20th century studies showed that if the mass of a point-like object was large enough, the curvature of space-time would be so large that even light would not be able to escape the area. The point at which this occurs is now referred to as the event horizon and can be described by the Schwarzschild radius: $r = 2GM/c^2$ ^{1;2}. Work by Finkelstein, Kruskal, and Szekeres also provided for a coordinate system beyond the Schwarzschild radius^{3;4}. The consequence of this is that while it is possible to model space-time on both sides of the event horizon, the two sides are unable to interact^{2;5}. Also of note is that extending these coordinates beyond the event

horizon results in the space coordinate becoming "time-like." Perhaps the most famous example of this is Minkowski's solutions to Einstein's equations which are the basis for the famous Penrose diagrams⁶.

One obvious issue with such a boundary is the apparent violation of the second law of thermodynamics, which states that for a spontaneous process to occur the entropy of a system, in this case the universe, must increase^{7;8}. However, it would appear that an object crossing the Schwarzschild limit would essentially be "lost" to the universe, effectively lowering the entropy. Steven Hawking proposed an explanation for this discrepancy by evoking the Davies-Unruh effect^{9;10}. In summary, the ground state, or vacuum state, of a quantized field depends on the reference point of the observer, therefore, an accelerating object will experience a different vacuum state than a stationary one. This is manifest by a perceived increase in the thermal energy of the vacuum for an accelerating observer^{10;11}. Near the event horizon an object is expected to be accelerated toward the point-like singularity, and therefore, an increase in thermal energy is expected. Interestingly, for an object accelerating immediately above the event horizon this would suggest that there must be some source of particles from beyond the event horizon in order for the thermal energy of the vacuum to increase. This was dubbed as Hawking radiation. Hawking showed the relation between the temperature and entropy of a black hole, in which the most interesting discovery was perhaps the revelation that the entropy (S) is related to the area of the sphere that makes up the Schwarzschild radius rather than the internal volume: $S = \pi R^2$ ¹².

Moreover, gravitational waves have been experimentally observed at the Laser Interferometer Gravitational-Wave Observatory (LIGO)^{13;14}. This empirical evidence of the existence of gravitational waves has further peaked scientific interest in determining their spectroscopic properties. Interestingly, recent scientific theory suggests that superconducting materials may also be used to reflect high frequency gravitational waves^{15;16}. Studies have also postulated that highly energetic particles, such as those found in the upper atmosphere or inside particle accelerators, may be converted into microscopic black holes¹⁷. It should be noted that the Hawking radiation of a black hole is inversely proportional to its mass, with microscopic black holes postulated to emit a high dose of radiation and quickly evaporate, this evaporation is also predicted to have a quantized nature¹⁸. While the emission profiles of black holes have been of interest for several decades, the black-box nature of the objects makes it difficult to determine how such a radiation field would behave beyond the Schwarzschild radius.

The photon is perhaps the most ideal particle to study in its behavior of space-time due to the fact that it conveniently travels at c , the maximum velocity allowed for any particle. Modeling the behavior of "light-like" geodesics is also a convenient tool to predict the behavior of gravitation fields in Schwarzschild spacetime¹⁹⁻²¹. Moreover, it is also a particle which has fundamental connections to quantum mechanics since photons are the force carriers of electromagnetism²². It is therefore reasonable to assume that any grand theory that attempts to unify general relativity with quantum mechanics will have to explain the behavior of photons which is satisfactory to both regimes. Being the force carriers of electromagnetism, the photon is responsible for mediating the interactions between particles of matter. The time dependent Schrodinger equation can be used to describe the evolution of a state in

time^{23;24}. In theory, the Schrodinger equation can be integrated over all time to determine the evolution of a particle. However, in practice, this is highly complex and approximations such as perturbation theory, are used. In perturbation theory, when a photon interacts with a molecule, the latter's potential energy surface will become perturbed. Therefore, the evolution of this state can be closely estimated by making close approximations to the scale of the perturbation²⁴.

Because modern theories of spectroscopy rely on time dependency to model spectra, a unique phenomena arises near a singularity. The Schwarzschild metrics representing space increase to infinity, while the metric for time decreases to zero at the event horizon. However, extending the coordinates past the event horizon reverses this relationship^{20;25;26}. The goal of this manuscript is to attempt to describe the interaction of light and matter under such conditions.

2 Theory

2.1 Behavior of space and time near a massive point-like object

As stated in the introduction, the Schwarzschild metric can be used to model the curvature of space-time around a point-like mass. Equation 1 displays the Schwarzschild metric in its matrix form, with the $g_{\mu\nu}$ term representing the Einstein tensor where $r_s = \frac{2GM}{c^2}$ ¹. In order to map the Schwarzschild metric unto a two-dimensional surface the conversion factors in Equations 2 and 3 are used to convert the temporal and spatial dimensions respectively. Note that the r^2 and the $r^2 \sin^2\theta$ factors represent the spatial angles, for simplicity these factors will be ignored when simplifying Equation 1 down to a two-dimensional surface and only the g_{00} and g_{11} matrix terms representing the spatial and temporal dimensions will be considered. This plot of Equation 1 is seen in Figure 1. For further simplicity the graphic in Figure 2 describes the phenomenological behavior of space-time in the vicinity of a massive point-like object.

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} -(1 - \frac{r_s}{r}) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{(1 - \frac{r_s}{r})} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & r^2 \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$d\tau = -\sqrt{g_{00}}dt \quad (2)$$

$$ds = \sqrt{g_{11}}dr \quad (3)$$

The behavior of space and time around a point-like object is plotted using Equations 1-3 in Figure 1. Note that at a large distance from center mass the temporal and spatial factors both approach unity. Close to the center mass the temporal factor approaches zero, which can be understood as the object accelerating close to c , at which point extreme time dilation occurs, with massless particles traveling at

Figure 1: Two dimensional plot of the Schwarzschild metric transformed unto a two dimensional surface showing the behavior of the time (g_{00}) and space (g_{11}) around a point like object.

Figure 2: A summary of the behavior of space-time near a massive point-like object according the Equations 1-3. The spatial (x) direction is stretched closer to the mass, while the temporal (t) direction reduces to zero. The behavior is reversed beyond the Schwarzschild radius.

c understood as not experiencing time from their reference frame^{1;27}. Contrary, the spatial dimension approaches infinity near the event horizon of the point-like mass, signifying an object becomes infinitely stretched, which parries both, the holographic hypothesis of a black hole and the gravitational radiation theory²⁷⁻²⁹. Most interestingly, however, is what occurs once the equations are extended to the negative integers, which would represent the area inside the Schwarzschild radius. Note that in the negative area, it is the spatial factor which starts at zero and moves asymptotically to unity, while the temporal factor is near infinity in the vicinity of the back side of the event horizon. In effect, space and time in the vicinity of a massive point-like mass appear to behave in opposite manners^{21;30}. This behavior may have ramifications for molecular spectroscopy. For example, the question must be asked, if an atomic sized object were to tunnel past the Schwarzschild radius, how would one model it's spectroscopic behavior?

2.2 Basics principles of spectroscopy

The basic quantum nature of spectroscopy dates back to the Bohr description of the atom in which stationary states are first described using the Schrodinger equation as seen in Equations 4 and 5^{23;31;32}. Moreover, a key principal of quantum mechanics is that an arbitrary wavefunction can be written as a linear combination of states, as seen in Equation 6²⁴. Perhaps most importantly from a chemical standpoint, is that Equation 6 allows for the approximation of molecular orbitals by using a combination of atomic orbitals. In summary, a molecular orbital is the final wavefunction constructed from a combination of simpler wavefunctions. Finally, the probability of observing a wavefunction is represented by squaring its value and integrating over some space (which represents a boundary condition), as seen in Equation 7^{24;32}.

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = H\Psi \quad (4)$$

$$|\Psi_t\rangle = e^{\frac{-iEt}{\hbar}} |\Psi_0\rangle \quad (5)$$

$$\Psi_f = c_1\Psi_1 + c_2\Psi_2\dots = \sum_n c_n \Psi_n \quad (6)$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\Psi_{x,t}|^2 dx \quad (7)$$

The question may now arise, how do Equations 4-6 pertain to spectroscopic observations, particularly for chemical substances? In simple terms, when an oscillating electromagnetic field interacts with matter it will in turn create an oscillating field inside the matter. While the full definition of the degree of light interaction involves gauge fixing to describe the behavior of electric susceptibility of matter this

treatment is beyond the scope of this manuscript. A more intuitive approach is to use perturbation theory, in which states that when light interacts with matter it perturbs states within it. The degree of the perturbation can be estimated by expanding Equation 5 to Equation 8. Based on Equation 8 we can deduce that states can be combined with each other creating a linear super position, the space in which this linear combination occurs is referred to as the Hilbert space³³. Two main points must be taken away so far, in Hilbert space a wavefunction of a stationary state can be described by a linear combination of states, and that a stationary state is a quantum state that remains in the same state as time lapses, that is, it is independent of time. However, note that Hilbert space, is a vector space. Indeed, the wavefunction is, by definition, a linear combination of vectors, shown in Equation 9 where the wavefunction is in three dimensional vector space. The probability to observe any measurement outcome is equal to 1, a keen observer will notice that the vector space nature of this treatment means that the probability of observing a particle is actually determined by its scalar product. Notice that the probability of observing a particle is independent of time, hence the term “stationary state.” A unperturbed electron in a hydrogen atom is analogous to this stationary state, therefore one can think of the s orbital occupied by the electron as a stationary state, with the orbital itself simply being a probability density of the quantum particle’s wavefunction. Note that in the aforementioned example, the quantum particle remains at the same state independent of time. The obvious question now arises, if a hydrogen atom were to tunnel across the Schwarzschild radius would the stationary state still be independent of time? Worse still, if such a state were to be perturbed by a photon, how would it evolve?

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} = \sum_m e^{i \frac{E_n - E_m t}{\hbar}} \langle \Psi_n | H_{int} | \Psi_m \rangle c_m(t) \quad (8)$$

$$|\Psi_f\rangle = \sum_n c_n |\Psi_n\rangle = c_1 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + c_2 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + c_3 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

3 Spectroscopy beyond the event horizon

For this portion of the manuscript let us first ignore the quantum nature of particles and perform a thought experiment using a classical physics example. Imagine you are standing on the observation deck of the Empire State Building. You release a steel ball from the observation deck. What factors would be needed to calculate the energy of this ball as it travels toward the ground? Surely one would need to know the starting position, indeed this starting position would give the initial energy that the ball has since $PE=mgh$ ³⁴. Moreover, we know the total amount of energy is conserved: $PE=KE$ (assuming no air resistance). Once one knows the acceleration due to gravity, it would be simple to calculate the remaining kinetic and potential energy of the ball at any given time. However, note that other forces can act on the ball, a person standing nearby may hold a magnet which could overpower the force of gravity, pulling the ball up, likewise a sudden updraft may send it upwards.

In essence, the ball is free to go in any spatial direction (vector) which has the strongest force. However, the ball will always age, and is only free to flow in a single temporal direction. This scenario is somewhat analogous to a quantum particle in Hilbert space, where the particle has multiple vectors accessible to it, however, the equations are calculated only in a single temporal direction. Let's extend the ball throwing scenario to a case beyond the Schwarzschild radius, where the temporal and spatial properties of space-time are inverted. Now, the ball will always travel in a single spatial direction, however, it is now free to travel in any temporal direction. Now, let us extend the ball analogy to a quantized particle. Recall how an electron in the hydrogen atom is analogous to a stationary state of a wavefunction and Equation 7 can be used to estimate the probability of observing the state. In the case of an electron in a hydrogen atom projecting this probability would simply give its orbital, as seen in Figure 3. Note that the probability density of the electron is independent of time, that is, the quantum particle is equally as likely to be present at any given point, such as the probability being equal at point $x1$, and $y1$. As discussed in the introduction, crossing the Schwarzschild radius would result in the switching of the spatial and temporal dimensions. Therefore, the probability of finding the quantum particle would be independent of space, with its probability density dependent on time. While this seems counterintuitive for a simple atomic orbital, recall that a molecular orbital can be approximated as a linear combination of atomic orbitals, as described in Equation 6. The overlap integral of the two wavefunctions, $\Psi_{12} = \langle \Psi_1 | \Psi_2 \rangle = \int \int \Psi_1 \Psi_2 dx dy$, determines the molecule's bond strength. In this case two hydrogen atoms forming a H_2 molecule. Note that in molecular orbital theory this integral take place over all space, however, in a situation in which the temporal and spatial dimensions are inverted, the integral would take place over all time. The overlap integral is one of the factors determining bond strength, typically, the greater the overlap in space, the stronger the bond. By inverting the dimensions of space and time, the two orbitals would, therefore, have to overlap in time to form molecular bonds.

Recall that when an electromagnetic field interacts with a molecule the electric field of the molecule becomes perturbed, thus, perturbation theory is used to estimate this interaction. Therefore, let us ponder how the switching of the temporal and spatial dimensions would impact perturbation theory. The final wavefunction can be estimated by the first order perturbative correction seen in Equation 10.

$$|\Psi\rangle = |\Psi_n\rangle + \frac{\langle \Psi_m | V | \Psi_n \rangle}{E_m - E_n} |\Psi_m\rangle \quad (10)$$

The concept of the potential energy surface must now also be introduced. A potential energy surface (PES) is a mathematical function which results from the Born-Oppenheimer approximation. Because the nucleus of atoms can be treated as stationary as compared to electrons. Therefore, bond energies can be more easily calculated since molecular bonds can now be defined as measuring energy between two molecules exchanging electrons as a function of one or more coordinates, typically distance or angle³⁵. Perhaps the most familiar is the $PES = 1/2(kx^2)$ formalism in which the potential energy is expressed in terms of a spring constant k and bond distance x . The spring constant is itself defined as $k = \omega^2 m$ where omega is the

Figure 3: Left) An s orbital projected onto a 2 dimensional space. Right) Visualization of a linear combination of two atomic orbitals, the overlap integral results in bond formation.

frequency of the vibrational energy level and m is the reduced mass^{24;32}. In Figure 4 the PES is drawn as function of energy versus bond length between two molecules. When a quantum particle such as a photon interacts with this system it is perturbed in space, as seen on the right side of Figure 4. Typically, the wavefunction of the perturbed system could be estimated by Equation 10, which integrates over space. However, once again, in an environment where the temporal and spatial dimensions are inverted we would have to integrate over time.

Figure 4: Left) The potential energy surface of a hypothetical bond at rest as a measure of bond length between two atoms. Right) The potential energy after interaction with a photon.

We can break down the sequence of events that occur to a H_2 molecule interacting with a photon into its temporal and spatial dimensions. At t_1 the molecule is at rest, at t_2 the interaction occurs and the molecule is perturbed, moving freely in the x , y , z , and θ directions, at t_3 the molecule returns to its initial state. The molecule must move forward in the temporal direction, however, it is free to move anywhere in the spatial direction. However, when interacting with a photon beyond the Schwarzschild radius the H_2 molecule must always move toward the singularity in the spatial direction. Therefore, at position x_1 it will start at temporal position t_1 , however, at position x_2 it may move to temporal position $t_1 + c$ where c may represent a positive or negative value.

4 Conclusion

The consequences of examining how light and matter interact on either side of the Schwarzschild radius have interesting consequences. First, we must remember that while the number of vectors in the space dimension is technically infinite, although limiting to the x , y directions for simplicity is a reasonable assumption. However, the temporal dimension only has two vectors, the positive and negative. This suggests that an object crossing the Schwarzschild radius in which the temporal and spatial dimensions switch would now be limited to only two spatial dimensions as well, to and from the singularity. Moreover, it appears to alter one of the more fundamental rules of spectroscopy, Fermi's golden rule seen in Equation 11. The rule states that the rate of transition per unit time from the initial to a final state is dependent on the density of final states as well as the coupling between the initial and final states. However, now the rate would depend on unit of space. Conceptually these concepts are sound since the molecule must move toward the singularity. Therefore, any photophysical process must occur as a function of the molecule traveling toward its final destination.

$$\Gamma_{if} = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle f | H | i \rangle|^2 \rho E_f \quad (11)$$

Finally, it is useful to include the basic particle in a box analogy when thinking about the energy of a quantum particle: $E = (n^2 h^2 / (8mL^2))$ ^{24;32;36}. Typically, L represents the length of the box, however, if we go beyond the Schwarzschild radius it would represent the time. Therefore, the energy of a quantum particle would depend on time, with the broadest barriers being the singularity and the event horizon. Typically, we summarize that a molecule has smaller absorptive energy as its spatial size L increases. However, beyond the Schwarzschild radius we can see that the energy of the molecule would depend on time, when the molecules has little time to the singularity it would have the largest energy. Finally, because the quantum wavefunction would be free to evolve in either temporal direction, this would suggest as it travels toward the singularity the wavefunction could evolve to energy states that were occupied at a previous time.

A studious observer may note that the Schwarzschild coordinates used through the manuscript are valid for a distant observer. However, all spectroscopy by its nature relies on photons to measure distant phenomena.

Through this manuscript the concepts of space-time and quantum mechanics have been discussed. Particularly, the behavior of light and matter in the vicinity of a non-rotating, Schwarzschild black hole were examined using perturbation theory. While it is impossible to definitively know how a quantum particle would behave beyond a Schwarzschild radius until a theory unifying quantum mechanics and general relativity is formed, applying current theories to the question is still an important exercise which can spur new ideas and discussions among the scientific community. For example, novel meta-materials such as those possessing a negative refractive index, which have been experimentally tested, started out as purely theoretical constructs³⁷.

5 Disclosures

This article reflects the views of the authors and should not be construed to represent the views or policies or guarantees of any organizations with which the authors may be affiliated or employed with. The author declares that they have no known competing financial interests that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. All relevant data is presented within the paper.

References

- [1] W. Borgiel, *Differential Geometry and its Applications* **29**, S207 (2011), :<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.difgeo.2011.04.042>.
- [2] H. A. Atwater, *Introduction to General Relativity: International Series of Monographs in Natural Philosophy*, Vol. 63 (Elsevier, 2013).
- [3] K. Martel and E. Poisson, *American Journal of Physics* **69**, 476 (2001), :<https://doi.org/10.1119/1.1336836>.
- [4] J. M. Hill and J. O’Leary, *Royal Society Open Science* **5**, 171109 (2018), :<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171109>.
- [5] R. B. Mann and R. G. Mclenaghan, *General Relativity And Relativistic Astrophysics-Proceedings Of The 5th Canadian Conference* (World Scientific, 1994).
- [6] S. Maity, M. A. Shaikh, P. Tarafdar, and T. K. Das, *Physical Review D* **106**, 044062 (2022), :<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.106.044062>.
- [7] C. Tsallis and L. J. Cirto, *The European Physical Journal C* **73**, 1 (2013), :<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-013-2487-6>.
- [8] I. P. Neupane, *International Journal of Modern Physics A* **24**, 3584 (2009), :<https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217751X09047235>.
- [9] S. P. Kim, *International Journal of Modern Physics D* **25**, 1645005 (2016), :<https://doi.org/10.1142/S021827181645005X>.

- [10] A. Mukherjee, S. Gangopadhyay, and A. S. Majumdar, *Physical Review D* **108**, 085018 (2023), [:https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.108.085018](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.108.085018).
- [11] L. C. Crispino, A. Higuchi, and G. E. Matsas, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **80**, 787 (2008), [:https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.80.787](https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.80.787).
- [12] S. W. Hawking, G. T. Horowitz, and S. F. Ross, *Physical Review D* **51**, 4302 (1995), [:https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.51.4302](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.51.4302).
- [13] D. Castelvecchi and A. Witze, *Nature news* **11** (2016), [:https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2016.19361](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature.2016.19361).
- [14] B. P. Abbott, R. Abbott, T. D. Abbott, M. R. Abernathy, F. Acernese, K. Ackley, C. Adams, T. Adams, P. Addesso, R. X. Adhikari, *et al.*, *The Astrophysical Journal* **839**, 12 (2017), [:https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa677f](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aa677f).
- [15] A. Avramenko, *Optica Applicata* **54** (in print).
- [16] S. J. Minter, K. Wegter-McNelly, and R. Y. Chiao, *Physica E: Low-dimensional Systems and Nanostructures* **42**, 234 (2010), [:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2009.06.056](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2009.06.056).
- [17] P. C. Argyres, S. Dimopoulos, and J. March-Russell, *Physics Letters B* **441**, 96 (1998), [:https://doi.org/10.1016/S0370-2693\(98\)01184-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0370-2693(98)01184-8).
- [18] J. D. Bekenstein and V. F. Mukhanov, *Physics Letters B* **360**, 7 (1995), [:https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693\(95\)01148-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693(95)01148-J).
- [19] D. N. Blaschke and H. Steinacker, *Classical and Quantum Gravity* **27**, 185020 (2010), [:https://doi.org/10.1088/0264-9381/27/18/185020](https://doi.org/10.1088/0264-9381/27/18/185020).
- [20] G. Hahne, *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and General* **35**, 7101 (2002), [:https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/35/33/309](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/35/33/309).
- [21] M. D. Kruskal, *Physical review* **119**, 1743 (1960), [:https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.119.1743](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.119.1743).
- [22] J. Williamson, in *The Nature of Light: What are Photons? VI*, Vol. 9570 (SPIE, 2015) pp. 341–355, [:https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2188259](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.2188259).
- [23] A. M. Kelley, *Condensed-phase molecular spectroscopy and photophysics* (John Wiley & Sons, 2022).
- [24] P. W. Atkins, J. De Paula, and J. Keeler, *Atkins' physical chemistry* (Oxford university press, 2023).
- [25] R. Ruffini and J. A. Wheeler, *Physics today* **24**, 30 (1971), [:https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3022513](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3022513).
- [26] N. Bodendorfer, F. M. Mele, and J. Münch, *Classical and Quantum Gravity* **36**, 195015 (2019), [:https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6382/ab3f16](https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6382/ab3f16).

- [27] F. A. Pirani, Physical Review **105**, 1089 (1957), :<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRev.105.1089>.
- [28] R. Bousso, Reviews of Modern Physics **74**, 825 (2002), :<https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.74.825>.
- [29] S. R. Roy and D. Sarkar, Physical Review D **92**, 126003 (2015), :<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.92.126003>.
- [30] F. Soltani, Physical Review D **108**, 124002 (2023), :<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.108.124002>.
- [31] J. L. Heilbron, American Journal of Physics **49**, 223 (1981), :<https://doi.org/10.1119/1.12521>.
- [32] A. G. Avramenko and M. Spiehs, Issues of Chemistry & Chemical Technology/Voprosy Khimii & Khimicheskoi Tekhnologii (2024), :<https://doi.org/10.32434/0321-4095-2024-154-3-5-15>.
- [33] S. Mukamel, “Principles of nonlinear optical spectroscopy,” (1995).
- [34] E. Hecht, European Journal of Physics **37**, 065804 (2016), :<https://doi.org/10.1088/0143-0807/37/6/065804>.
- [35] D. G. Truhlar, R. Steckler, and M. S. Gordon, Chemical Reviews **87**, 217 (1987), :<https://doi.org/10.1021/cr00077a011>.
- [36] A. Avramenko, Physics and Chemistry of Solid State **25**, 478 (2024), :<https://doi.org/10.15330/pcss.25.3.478-484>.
- [37] C. M. Soukoulis and M. Wegener, Nature photonics **5**, 523 (2011).